

NATIONAL BUREAU OF STATISTICS

Nigerian Domestic and Foreign Debt

(Q1 2019)

Report Date: July 2019

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Executive Summary

Nigerian States and Federal Debt Stock data as at 31st March 2019 reflected that the country's total public debt portfolio stood at N24.95trn.

Further disaggregation of Nigeria's total public debt showed that N7.86trn or 31.51% of the debt was external while N17.08trn or 68.49% of the debt was domestic.

Similarly, total domestic debt was N3.97 trillion with Lagos state accounting for 13.64% of the total domestic debt stock while Yobe State has the least debt stock in this category with a contribution of 0.68% to the total domestic debt stock.

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

ABIA STATE

Land Area: 2,440 sq mi

Population: 3,616,382

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N55,326,313,520.16

IGR As At Q4 2018

N14,834,904,447.49

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$98,582,798.91

30 June 2018

\$100,217,589.59

Total (\$)

\$98,582,798.91

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-1.63%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N67,017,185,656.92

DEBT STOCK (N)

N62,849,599,630.68

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-6.2%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

ADAMAWA STATE

Land Area: 14, 254 sq mi

Population: 4,111,706

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N49,510,206,574.39

IGR As At Q4 2018

N6,204,876,665.62

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$91,290,423.73

\$6,500,000.00

30 June 2018

\$57,860,541.54

Total (\$)

\$97,790,423.73

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

69.01%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N89,659,119,455.46

DEBT STOCK (N)

N97,153,965,072.71

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

8.4%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

AKWA IBOM STATE

Land Area: 2,734 sq mi

Population: 5,272,029

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N202,365,072,520.00

IGR As At Q4 2018

N24,210,810,102.72

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

ANAMBRA STATE

Land Area: 1,870 sq mi

Population: 5,356,592

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N55,249,945,897.30

IGR As At Q4 2018

N19,305,267,646.94

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$107,041,487.48

30 June 2018

\$107,438,517.03

Total (\$)

\$107,041,487.48

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-0.37%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N33,490,668,536.72

DEBT STOCK (N)

N33,490,668,536.72

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

0.0%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

BAUCHI STATE

Land Area: 18, 965 sq mi

Population: 6,286,719

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N54,020,849,574.38

IGR As At Q4 2018

N9,690,832,177.58

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$133,930,757.08

30 June 2018

\$134,907,612.92

Total (\$)

\$133,930,757.08

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-0.72%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N92,367,170,606.61

DEBT STOCK (N)

N93,319,627,053.30

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

1.0%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

BAYELSA STATE

Land Area: 8,150 sq mi

Population: 2,204,648

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N153,104,866,273.54

IGR As At Q4 2018

N13,636,545,716.78

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$56,623,178.71

30 June 2018

\$57,256,211.04

Total (\$)

\$56,623,178.71

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-1.11%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N130,043,473,800.97

DEBT STOCK (N)

N133,339,375,587.91

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

2.5%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

BENUE STATE

Land Area: 13,150 sq m

Population: 5,553,037

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N55,441,078,188.73

IGR As At Q4 2018

N11,215,482,725.16

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$39,610,851.64

30 June 2018

\$34,750,363.40

Total (\$)

\$39,610,851.64

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

13.99%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N97,347,605,190.14

DEBT STOCK (N)

N96,905,502,591.02

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-0.5%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

BORNO STATE

Land Area: 22, 316 sq mi

Population: 5,635,544

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N63,271,702,953.51

IGR As At Q4 2018

N6,524,300,904.06

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$21,618,240.11

30 June 2018

\$22,292,486.47

Total (\$)

\$21,618,240.11

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-3.02%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N68,381,705,608.58

DEBT STOCK (N)

N78,259,334,907.05

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

14.4%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

CROSS RIVER STATE

Land Area: 7,782 sq mi

Population: 3,741,838

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N36,954,686,823.12

IGR As At Q4 2018

N17,552,112,937.09

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$144,873,736.81

\$43,900,000.00

30 June 2018

\$193,796,061.81

Total (\$)

\$188,773,736.81

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.59%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N167,955,848,722.32

DEBT STOCK (N)

N167,252,341,140.66

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-0.4%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

DELTA STATE

Land Area: 6,833 sq mi

Population: 5,460,311

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N213,634,192,630.29

IGR As At Q4 2018

N58,439,598,672.31

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EBONYI STATE

Land Area: 2,136 sq mi

Population: 2,791,167

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N44,955,009,442.29

IGR As At Q4 2018

N6,144,587,065.65

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$66,653,026.12

30 June 2018

\$67,901,721.07

Total (\$)

\$66,653,026.12

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-1.84%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N55,597,352,310.28

DEBT STOCK (N)

N55,597,352,310.28

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

0.0%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EDO STATE

Land Area: 6,873 sq mi

Population: 4,109,499

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N69,169,646,683.36

IGR As At Q4 2018

N28,425,496,842.23

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$276,253,922.96

30 June 2018

\$279,029,896.21

Total (\$)

\$276,253,922.96

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-0.99%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N86,820,254,212.61

DEBT STOCK (N)

N86,367,405,983.76

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-0.5%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EKITI STATE

Land Area: 2,453 sq mi

Population: 3,157,552

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N39,325,661,893.63

IGR As At Q4 2018

N6,465,374,250.65

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$106,208,598.19

30 June 2018

\$97,994,770.66

Total (\$)

\$106,208,598.19

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

8.38%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N118,011,414,814.34

DEBT STOCK (N)

N118,011,414,814.34

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

0.0%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

ENUGU STATE

Land Area: 2,765 sq mi

Population: 4,263,786

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N53,104,455,149.91

IGR As At Q4 2018

N22,145,937,216.00

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$119,677,662.23

\$6,500,000.00

30 June 2018

\$127,952,029.92

Total (\$)

\$126,177,662.23

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-1.39%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N55,032,067,848.83

DEBT STOCK (N)

N55,882,997,585.01

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

1.5%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

GOMBE STATE

Land Area: 7, 246 sq mi

Population: 3,140,189

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N43,808,127,576.77

IGR As At Q4 2018

N7,343,549,621.53

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW (\$))

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$38,500,292.18

30 June 2018

\$100,217,589.59

Total (\$)

\$37,406,069.57

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.84%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N63,337,930,142.60

DEBT STOCK (N)

N76,894,514,835.51

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

21.4%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

IMO STATE

Land Area: 2,140 sq mi

Population: 5,214,833

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N54,181,645,137.53

IGR As At Q4 2018

N14,884,271,810.31

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$59,515,586.62

30 June 2018

\$61,277,993.68

Total (\$)

\$59,515,586.62

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.88%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N98,782,494,271.48

DEBT STOCK (N)

N97,851,149,167.90

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-0.9%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

JIGAWA STATE

Land Area: 8,940 sq mi

Population: 5,640,592

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N60,327,926,310.61

IGR As At Q4 2018

N9,246,250,836.03

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$32,008,444.77

30 June 2018

\$32,800,038.17

Total (\$)

\$32,008,444.77

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.41%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N35,163,169,800.26

DEBT STOCK (N)

N38,227,157,463.84

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

8.7%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

KADUNA STATE

Land Area: 17,781 sq mi

Population: 7,976,735

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

68,849,941,237.76

IGR As At Q4 2018

N29,446,386,924.74

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$227,252,685.58

30 June 2018

\$232,965,533.73

Total (\$)

\$227,252,685.58

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.45%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N84,637,112,775.54

DEBT STOCK (N)

N93,203,947,964.61

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

10.1%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

KANO STATE

Land Area: 7,773 sq mi

Population: 12,591,871

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N84,205,898,067.21

IGR As At Q4 2018

N44,107,375,284.25

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

KATSINA STATE

Land Area: 9,341 sq mi

Population: 7,569,751

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N61,651,483,460.58

IGR As At Q4 2018

N6,961,870,329.00

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$62,133,706.90

30 June 2018

\$64,757,964.40

Total (\$)

\$62,133,706.90

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-4.05%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N30,852,661,159.10

DEBT STOCK (N)

N67,098,008,669.65

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

117.5%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

KEBBI STATE

Land Area: 14,200 sq mi

Population: 4,286,319

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N54,580,176,454.57

IGR As At Q4 2018

N4,881,961,005.78

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$45,605,534.73

30 June 2018

\$46,759,780.42

Total (\$)

\$45,605,534.73

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.47%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N67,442,333,186.56

DEBT STOCK (N)

N67,037,456,840.31

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-0.6%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

KOGI STATE

Land Area: 11,519 sq mi

Population: 4,324,074

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N53,376,978,657.34

IGR As At Q4 2018

N19,311,789,037.16

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$31,584,158.36

30 June 2018

\$32,371,905.62

Total (\$)

\$31,584,158.36

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.43%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N84,922,376,449.78

DEBT STOCK (N)

N96,677,066,212.09

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

13.8%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

KWARA STATE

Land Area: 14, 218 sq mi

Population: 3,086,249

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N44,573,231,265.18

IGR As At Q4 2018

N23,046,944,295.60

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$48,599,040.43

30 June 2018

\$49,871,457.19

Total (\$)

\$48,599,040.43

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.55%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N59,135,900,168.96

DEBT STOCK (N)

N59,576,712,572.23

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

0.7%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

LAGOS STATE

Land Area: 1,381 sq mi

Population: 12,100,616

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N119,024,027,795.55

IGR As At Q4 2018

N382,181,548,627.13

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$1,282,598,935.47

\$143,830,000.00

30 June 2018

\$,451,639,937.86

Total (\$)

\$1,426,428,935.47

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-1.74%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N530,243,773,934.40

DEBT STOCK (N)

N542,231,174,761.82

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

2.3%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

NASARAWA STATE

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 2,439,113

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N47,550,214,527.98

IGR As At Q4 2018

N7,566,920,656.91

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$59,183,665.51

30 June 2018

\$61,495,066.44

Total (\$)

\$59,183,665.51

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-3.76%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N85,363,486,609.87

DEBT STOCK (N)

N89,953,619,684.92

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

5.4%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

NIGER STATE

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 5,343,260

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N57,521,609,575.99

IGR As At Q4 2018

N10,432,190,956.63

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$54,845,344.97

\$6,500,000.00

30 June 2018

\$55,747,995.99

Total (\$)

\$61,345,344.97

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

10.04%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N41,831,488,692.26

DEBT STOCK (N)

N43,414,653,538.03

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

3.8%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

OGUN STATE

Land Area: 6,556.23 sq mi

Population: 5,024,191

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N39,644,151,088.38

IGR As At Q4 2018

N84,554,199,593.67

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

ONDO STATE

Land Area: 6,000 sq mi

Population: 4,515,660

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N64,686,727,822.91

IGR As At Q4 2018

N24,788,059,725.53

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$79,854,005.14

30 June 2018

\$81,417,458.58

Total (\$)

\$79,854,005.14

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-1.92%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N49,123,506,028.25

DEBT STOCK (N)

N56,959,970,712.20

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

16.0%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

OSUN STATE

Land Area: 3,572 sq mi

Population: 4,536,877

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N22,837,305,434.52

IGR As At Q4 2018

N10,381,663,677.98

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

OYO STATE

Land Area: 10,986 sq mi

Population: 7,540,300

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N59,289,159,988.50

IGR As At Q4 2018

N24,635,074,074.49

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$104,997,383.47

30 June 2018

\$106,334,516.11

Total (\$)

\$104,997,383.47

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-1.26%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N91,515,756,366.15

DEBT STOCK (N)

N94,140,261,739.96

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

2.9%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

PLATEAU STATE

Land Area: 11, 936 sq mi

Population: 4,075,392

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N43,885,148,418.60

IGR As At Q4 2018

N12,726,479,548.41

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$28,874,208.63

30 June 2018

\$29,696,386.15

Total (\$)

\$28,874,208.63

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.77%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N100,366,504,576.83

DEBT STOCK (N)

N98,585,866,556.33

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-1.8%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

RIVERS STATE

Land Area: 4,277 sq mi

Population: 7,023,942

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N172,627,019,316.70

IGR As At Q4 2018

N112,780,373,912.23

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

SOKOTO STATE

Land Area: 10,028 sq mi

Population: 4,831,152

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N54,460,056,835.47

IGR As At Q4 2018

N18,762,009,020.05

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

TARABA STATE

Land Area: 21, 032 sq mi

Population: 2,968,132

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N47,877,801,462.16

IGR As At Q4 2018

N5,968,809,583.11

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$21,611,262.68

30 June 2018

\$22,113,312.20

Total (\$)

\$21,611,262.68

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.27%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N61,508,573,011.13

DEBT STOCK (N)

N68,569,699,976.43

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

11.5%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

YOBE STATE

Land Area: 17, 568 sq mi

Population: 3,163,747

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N52,874,949,262.91

IGR As At Q4 2018

N4,382,259,456.05

External Debt Stock

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

ZAMFARA STATE

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N40,831,825,094.60

IGR As At Q4 2018

N8,206,695,592.14

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$33,524,208.01

30 June 2018

\$34,244,939.78

Total (\$)

\$33,524,208.01

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-2.10%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N59,900,241,661.65

DEBT STOCK (N)

N61,950,819,816.58

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

3.4%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

FCT

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Total FAAC Allocation 2018

N73,061,038,399.50

IGR As At Q4 2018

N65,519,663,654.82

External Debt Stock

MULTILATERAL (\$)

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$31,848,844.12

30 June 2018

\$32,833,430.20

Total (\$)

\$31,848,844.12

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

-3.00%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N164,245,377,802.60

DEBT STOCK (N)

N163,518,714,908.10

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

-0.4%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

SUB-TOTAL STATE & FCT

External Debt Stock (FGN)

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

FGN

External Debt Stock (FGN)

MULTILATERAL (\$)

\$7,008,095,136.98

BILATERAL (AFD) (\$)

\$120,153,811.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW) (\$)

\$2,747,046,800.00

COMMERCIAL (EURO BONDS & DIASPORA BOND)

\$11,168,352,000.00

30 June 2018

\$17,834,756,936.86

Total (\$)

\$21,043,647,747.98

GROWTH RATE (%) (JUNE-DEC 2018)

17.99%

Domestic Debt Stock

DEC 31 2018

N12,774,405,700,000.00

DEBT STOCK (N)

N13,113,420,290,000.00

GROWTH RATE (%) (DEC 2018 - MAR 2019)

2.7%

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

GRAND TOTAL

External Debt Stock (Grand Total)

Domestic Debt Stock

Note: Domestic Debt Stock for 31 States + FCT was as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for 5 States (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) was as at December 31, 2018

Domestic Debt Stock for Rivers was as at September 30, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT AS AT MARCH 31, 2019

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT MARCH 3, 2019

A

FGN + STATES & FCT ONLY

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (US\$'M)
\$25,609.63

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (N'M)
N7,860,875.93

% OF TOTAL
31.51%

TOTAL EXTERNAL DEBT

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (US\$'M)
\$25,609.63

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (N'M)
N7,860,875.93

% OF TOTAL
31.51%

B

FGN ONLY

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (US\$'M)
\$42,721.68

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (N'M)
N13,113,420.29

% OF TOTAL
52.56%

STATES & FCT

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (US\$'M)
\$12,942.77

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (N'M)
N3,972,784.37

% OF TOTAL
15.92%

TOTAL DOMESTIC DEBT

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (US\$'M)
\$55,664.46

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (N'M)
N17,086,204.66

% OF TOTAL
68.49%

C

TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT(A+B)

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (US\$'M)
\$81,274.09

TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT(A+B)

AMOUNT OUTSTANDING (N'M)
N24,947,080.59

Percentage of Total

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

Total

\$79,397.93

MULTILATERAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$40,155.70	\$24,965.28	\$14,438.12	-----	\$52.25	\$36.09	0.00	\$(1,138.13)	\$567.46	\$321.16

IBRD

Total

0.00

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

A.D.B

Total

\$24,684.07

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$10,000.00	\$14,684.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

IFAD

Total

\$1,900.24

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$1,702.60	\$565.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$(368.24)	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

A.D.F

Total **\$8,236.38** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$4,140.70	\$3,528.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$567.46	0.00

AGTF

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

IDA

Total **\$42,718.88** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$22,708.41	\$6,065.06	\$14,308.20	0.00	\$52.25	\$36.09	0.00	\$(451.13)	0.00	0.00

EDF

Total **\$1,123.77** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$1,001.73	\$122.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

BADEA

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

IDB

Total **\$734.59** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$602.27	0.00	\$129.92	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$(318.76)	0.00	\$321.16

Total **\$67,099.39** | Percentage of Total **18.78%**

BILATERAL

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$34,596.15	\$29,100.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	\$3,402.99	0.00

EXIM BANK OF CHINA

Total **\$66,691.46** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$34,596.15	\$28,819.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$3,275.79	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

NIGERIA COMMUNICATION SATELLITE

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA NATIONAL PUBLIC SECURITY COMM. SYS. PROJECT

Total **\$20,000.60** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$15,365.38	\$4,635.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (IDU KADUNA SECTION)

Total **\$25,032.05** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$19,230.77	\$5,801.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (LAGOS - IBADAN SECTION)

Total **\$4,861.87** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$3,352.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$1,509.22	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

NIGERIA ABUJA LIGHT RAIL PROJECT

Total **\$5,724.27** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$5,675.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$48.73	0.00

NIGERIA ICT INFRASTRUCTURE BACKBONE PROJECT

Total **\$1,169.59** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$1,161.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$7.60	0.00

NIGERIA FOUR AIRPORT TERMINALS EXPANSION PROJECT

Total **\$4,846.84** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$4,721.81	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$125.03	0.00

NIGERIAN ZUNGERU HYDROELECTRIC PROJECT

Total **\$4,361.17** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$3,471.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$890.14	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

NIGERIAN REHABILITATION AND UPGRADING OF ABUJA-KEFFI-MAKURDI ROAD PROJECT

Total **\$695.07** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$695.07	0.00

EXIM BANK OF INDIA

Total **\$258.41** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$157.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$101.37	0.00

FRENCH DEVELOPMENT AGENCY

Total **\$123.69** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$123.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

JICA

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

KFW

Total **\$25.83** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$25.83	0.00

Total

\$210,759.58

COMMERCIAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$210,759.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

210,759.58

EUROBONDS

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$210,759.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

5.125% EUROBOND 2018

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

6.75% EUROBOND 2021

Total **\$16,875.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$16,875.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

6.375% EUROBOND 2023

Total **\$15,940.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$15,940.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.875% EUROBOND 2032

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.625% EUROBOND 2047

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

6.5% EUROBOND 2027

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.143% EUROBOND 2030

Total **\$44,643.75** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$44,643.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.696% EUROBOND 2038

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.875% EUROBOND 2027

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

9.248% EUROBOND 2027

Total **\$11,560.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$11,560.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

8.747% EUROBOND 2031

Total **\$14,578.33** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$14,578.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.696% EUROBOND 2038

Total **\$48,100.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$48,100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

7.875% EUROBOND 2032

Total **\$59,062.50** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	\$59,062.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

DIASPORA BOND

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

5.625% DIASPORA BOND 2022

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

0.00

Percentage of Total

OTHERS

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

AGENCY FEES

Total **0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q1 2019

EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE

OIL WARRANT

Total

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total

\$357,256.90

TOTAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest
\$74,751.85	\$264,825.11	\$14,438.12	0.00	\$52.25
Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$36.09	0.00	\$(1,138.13)	\$3,970.45	\$321.16

Methodology

Data is supplied administratively by the Debt Management Office, Nigeria and verified and validated by the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria.

Nigeria's Actual External Debt Service Payments in First Quarter, 2019

Category	Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges	Total	Percentage of Total
MULTILATERAL	40,155.70	24,965.28	14,438.12	-	52.25	36.09	0.00	(1,138.13)	567.46	321.16	79,397.93	22.22%
IBRD	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
A.D.B	10,000.00	14,684.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	24,684.07	
IFAD	1,702.60	565.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	(368.24)	0.00	0.00	1,900.24	
A.D.F	4,140.70	3,528.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	567.46	0.00	8,236.38	
AGTF	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
IDA	22,708.41	6,065.06	14,308.20	0.00	52.25	36.09	0.00	(451.13)	0.00	0.00	42,718.88	
EDF	1,001.73	122.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,123.77	
BADEA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
IDB	602.27	0.00	129.92	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	(318.76)	0.00	321.16	734.59	
BILATERAL	34,596.15	29,100.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3,402.99	0.00	67,099.39	18.78%
EXIM Bank of China	34,596.15	28,819.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3,275.79	0.00	66,691.46	
Nigeria Communication Satellite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria National Public Security Comm. Sys. Project	15,365.38	4,635.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20,000.60	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Idu Kaduna Section)	19,230.77	5,801.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	25,032.05	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Lagos - Ibadan Section)	0.00	3,352.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,509.22	0.00	4,861.87	
Nigeria Abuja Light Rail Project	0.00	5,675.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	48.73	0.00	5,724.27	
Nigeria ICT Infrastructure Backbone Project	0.00	1,161.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.60	0.00	1,169.59	
Nigeria Four Airport Terminals Expansion Project	0.00	4,721.81	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	125.03	0.00	4,846.84	
Nigerian Zungeru Hydroelectric Project	0.00	3,471.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	890.14	0.00	4,361.17	
Nigerian Rehabilitation and Upgrading of Abuja-Keffi-Makurdi Road Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	695.07	0.00	695.07	
EXIM Bank of India	0.00	157.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	101.37	0.00	258.41	
French Development Agency	0.00	123.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	123.69	
JICA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
KFW	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	25.83	0.00	25.83	
COMMERCIAL	0.00	210,759.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	210,759.58	58.99%
EUROBONDS	0.00	210,759.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	210,759.58	
5.125% Eurobond 2018	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.75% Eurobond 2021	0.00	16,875.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	16,875.00	
6.375% Eurobond 2023	0.00	15,940.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15,940.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2032	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.000% Eurobond 2007	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.5% Eurobond 2007	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.125% Eurobond 2009	0.00	46,643.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	46,643.75	
7.000% Eurobond 2008	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.625% Eurobond 2007	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
8.250% Eurobond 2007	0.00	11,988.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	11,988.00	
6.125% Eurobond 2001	0.00	14,976.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	14,976.33	
7.000% Eurobond 2008	0.00	46,166.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	46,166.00	
7.000% Eurobond 2003	0.00	20,962.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20,962.00	
5.000% Eurobond 2002	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
5.000% Singapore Bond 2002	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OTHERS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00%
Agency Fees	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OIL WARRANT	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	
TOTAL	74,751.85	264,825.11	14,438.12	0.00	52.25	36.09	0.00	(1,138.13)	3,970.45	321.16	357,256.90	100%

**DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION
AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT MARCH 31, 2019**

SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK (N)
1	ABIA	62,849,599,630.68
2	ADAMAWA	97,153,965,072.71
3	AKWA IBOM	199,768,698,811.90
4	ANAMBRA	33,490,668,536.72
5	BAUCHI	93,319,627,053.30
6	BAYELSA	133,339,375,587.91
7	BENUE	96,905,502,591.02
8	BORNO	78,259,334,907.05
9	CROSS-RIVER	167,252,341,140.66
10	DELTA	223,442,257,101.69
11	EBONYI	55,597,352,310.28
12	EDO	86,367,405,983.76
13	EKITI	118,011,414,814.34
14	ENUGU	55,882,997,585.01
15	GOMBE	76,894,514,835.51
16	IMO	97,851,149,167.90
17	JIGAWA	38,227,157,463.84
18	KADUNA	93,203,947,964.61
19	KANO	121,305,201,113.25
20	KATSINA	67,098,008,669.65
21	KEBBI	67,037,456,840.31
22	KOGI	96,677,066,212.09
23	KWARA	59,576,712,572.23
24	LAGOS	542,231,174,761.82
25	NASARAWA	89,953,619,684.92
26	NIGER	43,414,653,538.03
27	OGUN	97,090,119,332.73
28	ONDO	56,959,970,712.20
29	OSUN	147,702,865,382.96
30	OYO	94,140,261,739.96
31	PLATEAU	98,585,866,556.33
32	RIVERS	225,592,469,150.22
33	SOKOTO	36,571,742,397.44
34	TARABA	68,569,699,976.43
35	YOBE	26,990,637,417.62
36	ZAMFARA	61,950,819,816.58
37	FCT	163,518,714,908.10
Total		3,972,784,371,341.75

Important Notes	
1	Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty (30) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto Taraba, Yobe and Zamafara) and FCT were as at March 31, 2019
2	* Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Five (5) States, (Anambra Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) were as at December 31, 2018
3	** Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018
	<i>Prepared as at Thursday, June 20, 2019</i>

Category	Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service Charge	Penalty Interest	Waiver/ Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges	Total	Percentage of Total
MULTILATERAL	40,155.70	24,965.28	14,438.12	-	52.25	36.09	0.00	(1,138.13)	567.46	321.16	79,397.93	22.22%
IBRD	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
A.D.B	10,000.00	14,684.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	24,684.07	
IFAD	1,702.60	565.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	(368.24)	0.00	0.00	1,900.24	
A.D.F	4,140.70	3,528.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	567.46	0.00	8,236.38	
AGTF	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
IDA	22,708.41	6,065.06	14,308.20	0.00	52.25	36.09	0.00	(451.13)	0.00	0.00	42,718.88	
EDF	1,001.73	122.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,123.77	
BADEA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
IDB	602.27	0.00	129.92	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	(318.76)	0.00	321.16	734.59	
BILATERAL	34,596.15	29,100.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3,402.99	0.00	67,099.39	18.78%
EXIM Bank of China	34,596.15	28,819.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3,275.79	0.00	66,691.46	
Nigeria Communication Satellite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria National Public Security Comm. Sys. Project	15,365.38	4,635.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20,000.60	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Idu Kaduna Section)	19,230.77	5,801.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	25,032.05	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project (Lagos - Ibadan Section)	0.00	3,352.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,509.22	0.00	4,861.87	
Nigeria Abuja Light Rail Project	0.00	5,675.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	48.73	0.00	5,724.27	
Nigeria ICT Infrastructure Backbone Project	0.00	1,161.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.60	0.00	1,169.59	
Nigeria Four Airport Terminals Expansion Project	0.00	4,721.81	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	125.03	0.00	4,846.84	
Nigerian Zungeru Hydroelectric Project	0.00	3,471.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	890.14	0.00	4,361.17	
Nigerian Rehabilitation and Upgrading of Abuja-Keffi-Makurdi Road Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	695.07	0.00	695.07	
EXIM Bank of India	0.00	157.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	101.37	0.00	258.41	
French Development Agency	0.00	123.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	123.69	
JICA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
KFW	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	25.83	0.00	25.83	
COMMERCIAL	0.00	210,759.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	210,759.58	58.99%
EUROBONDS	0.00	210,759.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	210,759.58	
5.125% Eurobond 2018	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.75% Eurobond 2021	0.00	16,875.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	16,875.00	
6.375% Eurobond 2023	0.00	15,940.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15,940.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2022	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.625% Eurobond 2047	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
6.5% Eurobond 2027	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.143% Eurobond 2030	0.00	44,643.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	44,643.75	
7.696% Eurobond 2038	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2027	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
9.248% Eurobond 2027	0.00	11,560.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	11,560.00	
8.747% Eurobond 2031	0.00	14,578.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	14,578.33	
7.696% Eurobond 2038	0.00	48,100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	48,100.00	
7.875% Eurobond 2032	0.00	59,862.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	59,862.50	
DIASPORA BOND	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
5.625% Diaspora Bond 2022	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OTHERS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00%
Agency Fees	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OIL WARRANT	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	
TOTAL	74,751.85	264,825.11	14,438.12	0.00	52.25	36.09	0.00	(1,138.13)	3,970.45	321.16	357,256.90	100%

Federal Government Domestic Debt Stock by Instrument as at March 31, 2019

Instruments	Amounts in Naira	% of Total
FGN Bonds	9,723,669,938,592.00	74.15%
FGN Savings Bond	9,705,516,000.00	0.07%
FGN Sukuk	200,000,000,000.00	1.53%
Green Bond	10,690,000,000.00	0.08%
Nigerian Treasury Bills	2,651,514,042,000.00	20.22%
Nigerian Treasury Bonds	150,988,000,000.00	1.15%
Promissory Notes	366,853,285,354.00	2.80%
TOTAL	13,113,420,781,945.00	100.00%

DEBT MANAGEMENT OFFICE
NIGERIA

Federal Government Actual Domestic Debt Service for January - March, 2019
(Amount in Naira)

Instruments	January	February	March	Total
NTBs				
Interest	74,142,567,148.83	29,683,398,145.71	17,094,009,726.78	120,919,975,021.32
Federal Govt. Bonds				
Interest	183,626,501,396.83	125,646,354,326.10	171,575,809,692.56	480,848,665,415.49
Treasury Bonds				
Interest	-	-	-	-
Principal	-	-	-	-
FGNSB				
Interest	100,501,149.44	92,516,590.62	154,897,577.45	347,915,317.51
FGN SUKUK				
Interest	-	-	-	-
FGN Green Bond				
Interest	-	-	-	-
TOTAL INTEREST	257,869,569,695.10	155,422,269,062.43	196,992,032,065.28	610,283,870,822.81

DDEBT MANAGEMENT OFFICE
NIGERIA

Nigeria's Total Public Debt Portfolio as at March 31, 2019

	Debt Category	Amount Outstanding	Amount Outstanding (₦'M)	% of Total
A.	Total External Debt	25,609.63	7,860,875.93	31.51%
	FGN + States & FCT only	25,609.63	7,860,875.93	31.51%
B.	Total Domestic Debt	55,664.46	17,086,204.66	68.49%
	FGN Only	42,721.68	13,113,420.29	52.56%
	States & FCT	12,942.77	3,972,784.37	15.92%
c.	Total Public Debt(A+B)	81,274.09	24,947,080.59	100%

Notes:

i. Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty (30) States, (Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto Taraba, Yobe and Zamafara) and FCT were as at March 31, 2019, while Domestic Debt Stock for Five (5) States, (Anambra, Borno, Ebonyi, Ekiti and Lagos) were as at December 31, 2018 and the Domestic Debt Stock Figure for Rivers State was as at September 30, 2018.

ii. CBN Official Exchange Rate of US\$1 to NGN306.95 was at March 31, 2019 was used in converting the Domestic Debts to USD.

Acknowledgements/Contacts

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